

EARTH SCIENCES

GEOLOGICAL CONDITIONS AND FEATURES OF MUD VOLCANOES IN THE SOUTH CASPIAN BASIN

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Abstract

The article deals with the development and spatial distribution of mud volcanoes in the waters of the South Caspian (in particular, the Baku archipelago), the characteristic features of the mud volcanic process, the main differences and similarities between marine and terrestrial mud volcanoes. It was found that by analyzing the products of mud volcanism it is possible to determine the age of deposits and the geological structure of the deep layers of the Earth. The geodynamic regime also affects the accumulation of hydrocarbons and the formation of traps. The system of anticlines of the Baku archipelago gives grounds to believe that there are favorable conditions for the accumulation of hydrocarbons in this region.

Keywords: Baku archipelago, Mud volcanoes, South Caspian Basin, Caspian Sea, geodynamic regime.

Mud volcanoes are developed worldwide mainly along the active tectonic belts which lie along the boundaries between actively converging tectonic plates. Mud volcanoes are known in Mexico, Trinidad, Venezuela, Colombia, Peru, Ecuador, Albania, Italy, Romania, the Iranian and Pakistan, India, Myanmar, Malaya, Indonesia, New Guinea, Taiwan, China, Japan, New Zealand, Russia (on the Kerch and Taman Peninsulas, and in southern Sakhalin), the western Caucasus, eastern Georgia, SW Turkmenistan. The greatest concentration, and most spectacular development, of mud volcanoes in any one region is the South Caspian Basin (Yakubov A.A, et al.,1970), These areas characterised by the following geological conditions: 1) High rates of sediment accumulation, and a thick (8-22 km) sedimentary succession reflected in the gravitational field (all areas of mud volcanism are associated with zones of extreme negative gravitational anomalies); 2) Depositional sequences composed in the lower part primarily of clastic and carbonate rocks, and the upper part of clastics with a predominance of argillaceous lithologies; 3) The sedimentary fill in the majority of basins associated with mud volcanism is dominated by synorogenic depositional sequences; 4) Active tectonic regimes, with disturbance and dislocation of the sedimentary sequence by folds and faults. Mud volcanoes in Azerbaijan lie on the SE flank of the Great Caucasus and its foothills, in the SE Shirvan region (N side of the Lower Kura Valley) and the Absheron and Baku Archipelagoes of the adjacent south Caspian Sea. The greatest concentration of mud volcanoes in the world is here in eastern Azerbaijan, with up to 220 recognised. The areas of Azerbaijan where mud volcanoes are developed include the following named oil and gas-bearing

regions: Precaspian-Guba, Absheron, Shemakha-Gobustan, Lower Kura, Baku Archipelago and the deep-water South Caspian (Fig. 1) [1-3]. The mud volcanoes of Azerbaijan have surface vents within deposits of various stratigraphic ages. In northern Gobustan the vents lie within the Cretaceous or sometimes Palaeogene deposits; in central Gobustan they are in the Palaeogene outcrop area; and in southern Gobustan, the Pre-Kura area, in the Absheron Peninsula and the Absheron and Baku Archipelagoes, they occur in areas of Oligocene to Pliocene surface geology. Fig.1. The map of mud volcano location in the South Caspian basin. In the study of mud volcanoes it is important to determine the specific stratigraphic unit to which they are "rooted". The root of a mud volcano is usually understood to refer to the deepest zone of mud volcano activity, from which the exit channel of the volcano begins. The stratigraphy of the root is usually determined by the microfauna contained in the solid phase of the material erupted, and also by comparative analysis of the lithological and petrographic properties of the breccia and the stratigraphic succession [4, 5]. The mud volcanoes of eastern Azerbaijan yield clasts with a very wide range of ages from Cretaceous, through Palaeogene to Neogene. Occasionally Jurassic clasts are recovered. However, the great majority of solid material (mud, and breccia clasts) coming out of mud volcanoes in Azerbaijan appears to derive from the Oligo-Miocene sediments, especially from the Maikop Suite. The solid material ejected sometimes includes rock fragments which are younger than those on the surface (eg. Demirchi); these are explained by the presence of thrusts.

Fig.1. The map of mud volcano location in the South Caspian basin.

Baku archipelago is located in the south of Absheron peninsula which consists more than 15 small islands such as “Boyuk Zira”, “Qum”, “Dash Zira”, “Gil” and etc. Majority of those small islands are of mud volcano origin. Gil, Khara Zira, “Sangi Mughan”, “Kara Su” and “Chigil” islands are good examples for mud volcano originated islands. Small proportion of islands, such as “Dash adalari” and “Sualti adalari” are of tectonic origin which means they were formed as a result of tectonic activities along convergent tectonic plate boundaries (Figure 1). Baku archipelago is rich in terms of oil and gas deposits as a result of several factors. Geodynamic regime and Mud volcanoes are one of those factors which has an impact on hydrocarbon generation of aforementioned archipelago.

Mud volcanoes are cone-shaped geological structures which forms as a result of extrusion of sediments with water and gas at the seafloor. Unlike magmatic volcanoes, mud volcanoes are less widespread around the world. More precisely, they usually form in places where there are oil and gas fields. There are more than 2000 known mud volcanoes around the world and 344 of them are located in Azerbaijan. Formation of mud volcanoes are related to geodynamic processes. There are 61 mud volcanoes in Baku Archipelago where 8 of them are of volcanic origin (Figure 1).

In general, by studying the products of mud volcanic eruptions, it is possible to obtain information about the depth of its formation, as well as the geolog-

ical structure of the deep layers of the earth and the geochemical processes that take place there. Geochemical analysis of mud volcanoes indicates that there are nearly 30 microelements mainly iron, nickel, chromium and etc. in erupted volcanic samples. The diversity of the location of these microelements suggests that the sources of mud volcanoes are at different depths. Thus, the study of mud volcano allows to create a fairly clear picture of the geological structure of the region. Among the mud volcanic erupted products of the Baku archipelago, the Miocene rock complexes as a whole contain more trace elements (except for lead, chromium, titanium and zinc) than in the Pliocene sediments [3]. Dolomite and siderites found in volcanic breccias show that rock samples are Oligocene-Miocene aged due to their petrographic properties.

When it comes to geodynamic regime, it is assumed that Baku archipelago fold zone is a tectonic extension of the structural elements of the South Gobustan and Lower Kura basin fold zones to the east and covers the folds extending into the sea. Baku archipelago consists of 7 anticlinal zones (Figure 2) :

1. Sangachal-Deniz-Khara-Zyra Deniz anticline
2. Alat Ridge anticline
3. Pirsaat-Sangi-Mughan-Dashly anticline
4. Galmaz-Bandovan-Mughan Deniz anticline
5. Yanan-Tava-Atashgah anticline
6. Neftchala-Kurdashi anticline zone
7. Kyzylgach anticline zone

Figure 2. Islands located in Baku archipelago

The anticlinal zones of the Baku Archipelago are strongly dislocated, in many cases asymmetric, the dip angles on the wings reach 35-40, sometimes 45-55. As the folds move away from the arch to the wings, the layers flatten sharply [6]. The formation of traps and the accumulation of hydrocarbons are related to the geodynamic regime, as the faulting process creates traps and cracks in which oil and gas migrate. In most fields (Sangachal-Deniz, Duvanni-Deniz, Khara-Zira, etc.), the accumulation of oil and gas is usually associated with tectonically screened traps. The study of non-anticline traps in this region and the prospects for oil and gas in connection with these traps is very important as well. Numerous oil and gas traces in drilled wells, including sea surface manifestations on islands and underwater mud volcanoes, once again confirm the existence of oil and gas deposits in the Baku archipelago.

Conclusion:

To conclude, Baku archipelago is known for the presence of numerous mud volcanoes and existence of geodynamical regime. By analyzing mud volcanic products one can determine the age of sediments and geological structure of deep layers of the Earth.

Geodynamical regime also has an influence on hydrocarbon accumulation and trap formation. The anticline system in the Baku archipelago gives us reason to

believe that there are suitable conditions for the accumulation of hydrocarbons in this area.

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